

Tension Pneumothorax After Surgical Tracheostomy: A Three-Case Series and Practical Prevention Bundle

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ABSTRACT

Background: Tracheostomy is a common procedure in the intensive care unit. Complications such as pneumothorax and tension pneumothorax, although uncommon can rapidly lead to cardiovascular collapse and mortality.

Case series: We describe three adult ICU patients who developed tension pneumothorax following surgical tracheostomy due to prolonged endotracheal intubation. All experienced abrupt ventilatory and haemodynamic deterioration shortly after the procedure or during early postoperative care. Although lung ultrasound (LUS) enabled immediate detection and timing-critical decompression, two of the patients however died few days afterwards.

Discussion: Pneumothorax after tracheostomy arises from pleural breach, posterior tracheal wall injury, barotrauma, or air dissection along pretracheal planes. Despite low incidence, pneumothorax features prominently in severe and fatal tracheostomy-related complications. LUS offers rapid bedside diagnosis, and procedural refinements reduce risk.

Conclusion: Tension pneumothorax is a rare but life-threatening complication of surgical tracheostomy. Standardized technique, structured tube exchange protocols, and routine post-procedure LUS may enhance safety. A peri-tracheostomy emergency pathway is recommended to forestall untoward mortality.

Keywords : Tracheostomy; Tension pneumothorax; Lung ultrasound; Intensive care unit; Airway complications; Endotracheal intubation.

Background

Tracheostomy is indicated in the intensive care unit following prolonged endotracheal intubation. Although generally safe, complications, including pneumothorax remain clinically significant in both surgical tracheostomy (ST) and percutaneous dilatational tracheostomy (PDT)^{1,2}. The incidence of

pneumothorax following tracheostomy is generally low approximately 1 percent, but markedly higher during emergency procedures¹. Large PDT series similarly document pneumothorax and surgical emphysema as recognized complications². A number of case reports have identified tension pneumothorax complicating after both ST and PDT, including in infants

and children^{3,4,5}. The anatomical variations including smaller pliable trachea, high pleural domes in the neck found in pediatric population make these complications mostly encountered during pediatric tracheostomies⁶

These events often present with sudden deterioration within minutes to hours of the procedure or during early tracheostomy tube manipulation^{3,4,5}.

Comparative evidence, including early meta-analyses and contemporary pooled analyses shows no difference in mortality between ST and PDT^{7,8,9,10}. Nevertheless, both procedures carry risk of severe complications, including pneumothorax, posterior wall injury, and false passage^{2,11,12}. Multiple studies

Case Presentations

Case 1

A 31-year-old female admitted to the intensive care unit with severe community pneumonia who developed septic shock in the course of her admission. She was intubated and placed on mechanical ventilation. She underwent elective ST on day 10 post intubation. The procedure was reported as uncomplicated. However, three days post tracheostomy and reconnection to the ventilator, she developed rising peak pressures, desaturation, and hypotension. Lung ultrasound showed absent lung sliding with a barcode sign on the right. Emergent needle decompression and chest tube placement was performed but the patient died two days later.

Case 2

A 3-year-old male patient with tracheal stenosis scheduled for an elective surgical tracheostomy. Eight days after, he devel-

Literature Review

Complications following tracheostomy are uncommon but clinically significant. A prospective surgical tracheostomy data report pneumothorax rates near 1 percent, with emergency procedures demonstrating substantially higher risk due to distorted anatomy and limited control of tissue planes¹. Large PDT series also identify subcutaneous emphysema and pneumothorax, though absolute incidence remains low².

Tension pneumothorax following both surgical, percutaneous tracheostomy and tube exchanges have been reported in adults and children^{3,4,5,7}. Early deterioration is typical, often occurring within minutes to hours. Fatal-case registries analysing severe PDT complications show that pneumothorax, while a minority contributor (≈ 6 percent), accounts for a consistent fraction of deaths, with 31 percent occurring intra-

have highlighted low tracheal windows, generous dissection, off-midline puncture, and barotrauma as mechanism of complication development^{12,13}.

Early identification of pneumothorax, especially tension pneumothorax is critical because haemodynamic instability may precede radiographic confirmation. Lung ultrasound (LUS) has superior diagnostic accuracy and speed compared with chest radiography and is now considered first-line for pneumothorax detection in critically ill patients^{14,15}.

These three cases illustrate classic patterns of deterioration and emphasise system-level strategies for safe tracheostomy practice in the ICU

oped tension pneumothorax with abrupt hypoxaemia and bradycardia. LUS revealed a left-sided pneumothorax. Chest decompression was immediately done and chest tube inserted, resulting in stable haemodynamics and oxygen saturation. He was discharged from the ICU after 27 days.

Case 3

A 70-year-old male with right chronic subdural haematoma. He was intubated and ventilated for eight days. The decision for elective surgical tracheostomy was taken due to prolonged endotracheal intubation. Some hours later, he developed sudden hypotension and hypoxaemia. LUS confirmed right-sided tension pneumothorax. Chest decompression with chest tube insertion was immediately done. Two days later, the patient succumbed to refractory hypotension and hypoxiaemia and died.

procedure and nearly half within seven days¹¹.

Meta-analyses comparing ST and PDT, including classical prospective-trial analyses⁷ and recent large-scale pooled studies^{9,10}, conclude that mortality is equivalent between techniques. However, PDT may confer lower risks of infection and peri-stomal bleeding, whereas ST carries less risk of posterior wall trauma; pneumothorax remains possible in both.^{8,9,10,11}

Mechanisms of development of pneumothorax following tracheostomy include, low tracheal windows that impinge on pleural domes^{12,13}, excessive lateral or deep dissection enabling air tracking into mediastinum or pleural space¹³, posterior wall injury resulting in air leakage and barotrauma^{11,12} and false passage during exchange leading to rapid air misdirection^{7,12}.

The use of lung ultrasound helps with early and accurate diagnosis of pneumothorax, especially following tracheostomy. As a diagnostic tool, LUS demonstrates accuracy surpass-

Discussion

The three cases reported here reflect well-established patterns of tracheostomy-associated tension pneumothorax: early onset, abrupt ventilatory failure, and haemodynamic collapse. Similar presentations are well documented in prospective studies, meta-analyses, and international case literature.^{1,2,3,4,5}

Previous studies have highlighted the dangers of low tracheal windows, off-midline dissection, and excessive tissue disruption, especially in patients with small or anatomically challenging necks^{12,13}. These insights reinforce a “high-enough, midline, minimal-dissection” surgical philosophy consistent with expert reviews and contemporary technique guidance¹³.

Tracheostomy tube exchange represents another hazard period. Multiple case reports describe tension pneumotho-

sing chest radiography, enabling immediate identification of pneumothorax through absent lung sliding, barcode sign, and lung point¹⁴.

rax arising from posterior wall injury, false passage, or acute barotrauma during exchange attempts^{4,7,11}. These data justify structured “exchange time-outs”, with preoxygenation, anatomical reassessment, rescue equipment readiness, and immediate access to LUS.

Rapid recognition of pneumothorax is essential. LUS-first assessment of both hemithoraces immediately after any tracheostomy or exchange is supported by strong evidence for superior diagnostic accuracy and speed compared with radiography^{14,15}. Given that nearly half of fatal PDT complications occur within seven days¹¹, routine immediate and repeat scanning is warranted when airway pressures rise or oxygenation deteriorates.

Despite its low incidence, pneumothorax remains a serious and life-threatening complication of tracheostomy. A peritracheostomy tension pneumothorax pathway, including

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